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WTO TRADE DISPUTE MECHANISM IS MORE POWER-BASED THAN RULE-BASED

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1. Introduction

Trade plays a crucial role in establishing and maintaining state diplomatic relations. International trade provides countries with the opportunity to gain access to goods which cannot be produced locally (Mokgethi 2016). The theoretical reasoning in favour of international trade was first put forward by Adam Smith (1776) in his work entitled "*An enquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations*" where he argued that countries would benefit more when they engage in free trade and use their comparative advantage to specialise in the production of goods. Quest for the mutual benefits accruing to countries as a result of international trade gave rise to trade liberalization as well the need to sidestep discrimination policies that breed global economic and political crises. Thus, the formation of rule-based trading system of WTO that would monitor international trade and oversee the conducts of nation-members was expedient. This was in view of the widely held belief that the economic prosperity of every country will be enhanced by opening up the market and eliminating all forms of discrimination in trade relations (Domiter 2014).

1.1. Aim of the Study

This research aims to identify the shortfalls and gaps of the provisions in the Marrakech Agreement and MFN principles on trade dispute settlements.

1.2. Research Questions

To achieve the aim of the present study, this research raises the following questions:

1. Are there provisions in the Marrakech Agreements that stipulates rule-based and fair processes of trade dispute mechanisms in International trade?
2. To what extent is the application of WTO's DSU power-based in its dispute settlements approach?
3. How does the Dispute Settlement mechanism of the WTO give undue considerations for developed countries as against developing countries?

1.3. Research Hypothesis

WTO is more power-based than rule-based in trade dispute settlements.

2.0. ANALYSIS AND CRITIQUE

2.1. Emergence of World Trade Organisation

WTO was created on April 15 1994 by Uruguay Round negotiations. The emergence of the WTO in 1995 was primarily aimed at institutionalizing the General Agreement on Trade & Tariffs (GATT) that had been in operation since 1947. At the completion of the Uruguay Round of Multilateral Trade Negotiations and the eventual signing of the Marrakech Agreement, WTO emerged as an organization that supervises and liberalises trade among nations (Rena 2012). This global international organization oversees the rules of trade between nations by administering trade agreements, creating a forum for trade negotiations (Ullah 2022), resolving trade disputes between countries, monitoring the trade policies of member states, among other functions (Eleso 2006). Zoladkiewicz and Orłowska (2020) submitted that the essence of WTO was to preserve a rule-based regime that enables members to reduce trade barriers together with global integration in view.

Currently, the WTO constitutes of 164 countries that commonly agree to operate a non-discriminatory trading system under the framework of WTO principles. The founding principle of WTO is the Most-Favoured Nation (MFN) treatment (Ghaziani, Ghaziani & Ghaziani 2022) whereby members in the trading system are made to accord the most favourable regulatory treatments given to the product of any country at the time of export or import of similar products to every WTO member.

2.2. The Dispute Settlement Body.

During the Uruguay Round, member governments created a dispute settlement mechanism referred to as the Dispute Settlement Understanding – DSU which embodies the rules and procedures governing the settlement of disputes, to ensure that the highly negotiated trading rules of the WTO are respected and enforced. (WTO, 2022)

In explaining the theory and practice of developing country members in dispute settlement, WTO states that ‘such a system, to which all Members have equal access and in which decisions are made on the basis of rules rather than on the basis of economic power, empowers developing countries and smaller economies by placing “the weak” on a more equal footing with “the strong”’ (WTO, 2008).

Some DSU provisions that refer to developing countries include:

-Article. 8.10: ‘When a dispute is between a developing country Member and a developed country Member the panel shall, if the developing country Member so requests, include at least one panelist from a developing country Member.’

-Article 12.10: "In the context of consultations involving a measure taken by a developing country Member, the parties may agree to extend the periods established in Article 4:7 and 4:8. If, after the relevant period has elapsed, the consulting parties cannot agree that the consultations have concluded, the Chairman of the DSB shall decide, after consultation with the parties, whether to extend the relevant period and, if so, for how long."

-Article 12.11: "Where one or more of the parties is a developing country Member, the panel's report shall explicitly indicate the form in which account has been taken of relevant provisions on differential and more-favourable treatment for developing country Members that form part of the covered agreements which have been raised by the developing country Member in the course of the dispute settlement procedures."

-Article 4.10: "During consultations Members should give special attention to developing country Members' particular problems and interests."

2.3. MFN Principle

The Principle of Most-Favoured Nation enshrined in GATT Article I stipulates that the same treatment provided by one WTO member to any WTO member must be immediately meted out unconditionally to the rest of the WTO members. The treatments may be in form of favour, privilege, an advantage, or an immunity. Simply put, MFN principle enables members of WTO to receive the highest import quotas, the fewest trade barriers, and the lowest tariffs (or none at all). It was succinctly defined by Zoladkiewicz and Orłowska (2020) as "favour one, favour all" principle. Member states of WTO are subject to the MFN principle and mandated to grant every WTO member the treatment that are as favorable as those accorded to any other country (Weiler & Cho 2011).

Notwithstanding, the submission of Cebi and Ludema (2002) that the support for the Most-Favored-Nation (MFN) treatment as a fundamental basis for the formation of WTO is much diminished, hence the routine adoption of policies that circumvent MFN by industrialized countries. Such policies are exemplified in the match towards unilateral and regional initiatives by developed countries (Berger & Brandi 2016). Powerful nations that dominated international trade during the late 20th century deployed discriminatory trade instruments that violated MFN rule such as the case of *US – Wool Shirts and Blouses*. In this case, India lodged a complaint against the United States for imposing temporary safeguard measure in the form of a quota on certain imports from India. The ruling was in favour of India.

MFN principle entirely embodies the rule of non-discrimination, a key concept of World Trade Organization that addresses discrimination between and discrimination against other countries (Sheldon 2022). Trade discrimination is a major breeder of resentment among nations, triggering economic and political conflicts, and poisoning international relations. However, a notable exception to the principle of MFN is regional trade agreements which give member countries the power not to apply MFN principle towards their non-members. GATTs Article XXIV, enabling clause and Article V empower regional trade agreements which operate as reciprocity treaty and indirectly diminish the role and efficiency of MFN principle.

3.0. DEFICIENCIES OF THE DSU

3.1. Deficiency I: Power-Based Dispute Settlements Approach

On the mandate of ensuring a smooth, predictable and free flow of international trade among nations, the WTO has a well-laid out procedure for trade conflict resolution under the Dispute Settlement Understanding (Hoda 2021; Fietta 2005). This procedure prioritises trade dispute settlement by means of consultation whereby the countries involved iron out their differences themselves (Jakobsson 2011). When this move proves abortive, the dispute can then be brought to the WTO by the party who feels that its rights under the WTO agreements have been violated.

There are indications that these provisions are not applied in trade dispute settlements, as seen in the rulings of Dispute Settlement Understanding and the Appellate body. Although the Most Favoured Nation (MFN) principle is the cornerstone of the dispute resolution mechanism of WTO (Radi 2007), indications that this principle is largely power-based instead of being rule-based abound. This has adversely made trading rights depend on the economic and political clouts of developed nations to the disadvantage of developing countries.

The WTO is majorly criticized with respect to its trade dispute resolution (Schimanski 2022; McDougall 2018). When a panel is set up to investigate an infringement under the WTO agreements, a violation may be found. The best remedy recommended for such infringement is withdrawal of the violation. However, the WTO has no effective mechanism for ensuring that the losing party timely complies with the withdrawal of the violation. Lack of compliance with the ruling has continuously undercut trust in the rules-based principles of WTO (Schneider-Petsinger 2020). There are some instances whereby the losing party fails to comply or delays in complying with the reports of either the panel or the appellate body. In the case of *United States – Measures Affecting the Cross-Border Supply of Gambling and Betting Services* between the US and Antigua & Barbuda, the US contemptuously did not comply with

the recommended remedy even after the deadline of April 3, 2006, elapsed. WTO apparatus is supposed to be formally established in order to monitor the extent of compliance. Leaving compliance-monitoring to the winning party takes for granted the possibility that the losing party will not adequately follow the compliance to the ruling, especially when the winning party is a developing country. Developing countries with poor economic resources encounter huge difficulty in monitoring such compliance and they cannot actually do anything about this, portraying the dispute resolution mechanism of the WTO as power-based instead of rule-based.

3.2. Deficiency II: Undue Favour for Developed Countries as Against Developing Countries

Articles 21.7 and 21.8 of the DSU states that the interests of developing countries should be taken into considerations, but it doesn't state how this aim will be realised. According to Horn & Mavroidis, "Art. 27.2 DSU is intended to ensure that technical assistance will be given to developing countries in the context of Dispute Settlement. But, the technical assistance granted is both quantitatively and qualitatively inadequate; first, so far the WTO has put at the disposal of developing countries only two experts in the field working part time and two junior staff members to help these countries with their disputes, taking into account the number of disputes where developing countries are implicated, the above mentioned resources are simply inadequate and developing countries are often forced to rely on private lawyers, the costs of which should not be underestimated. (Horn and Mavroidis,1999)

WTO is originally geared towards ensuring that developing countries secure a share of the benefits of international trade (European Union, 2021). WTO introduced Special and differential treatment (SDT) in order to capacitate developing economies to make the most optimal use of the opportunities which WTO membership offers. A level playing ground is yet to be provided by the MFN principle which advocates that the best access conditions that have been conceded to one country must unconditionally be accorded to all other members of the WTO in order to provide every member state with the opportunity to benefit from trade treatments agreed between countries (Bronckers 2020), even those that have extreme negotiating leverage (Bown 2008). Although the WTO has recorded huge success in encouraging free trade, Herbert (2020) argued that this mostly favours developed countries that have the material, capital and technological resources which enable them to compete in a global economy. Ogbonna (2012) equally found the MFN rule wanting in that it is used by developing countries to deny market access to the developing countries by way of exposing developing countries to unequal and stiff competitive conditions.

A famous case that supports the above argument is *United States – Import prohibition of certain Shrimp and Shrimp products*, where Malaysia, India, Pakistan and Thailand lodged a complaint against the United States for banning importation of shrimp and shrimp products from these countries. The complainants alleged that such ban contravened The MFN rule of Article I, General Elimination of Quantitative Restrictions of Article XI and Non-discriminatory Administration of Quantitative Restrictions of Article XIII of the GATT 1994. A Panel was instituted by the Dispute Settlement Body after the requests made by the complainants to that effect. The US was found to have violated the WTO's rules guiding international trade and that the US' import ban on shrimp and shrimp product infringed the stipulations of Article XI:1 of the GATT 1994. It was further affirmed that such contravention could not be justified under the General Exceptions provided in Article XX of the GATT 1994. However, the US was not satisfied with the findings of the Panel and therefore appealed against it. The Appellate Body reversed the findings of the Panel and concluded that the US could apply domestic legislation for the purpose of protecting shrimps under the Article XX of the GATT 1994 in so far as such domestic legislation satisfies the non-discrimination criterion among the exporters. The Appellate Body, however, ruled that the measure applied by the US was not within the scope of measures that are allowed under Article XX of the GATT 1994, even though the measure qualified for a provisional justification (World Trade Organization 2010). The report of the Appellate Body and the modified report of the Panel were adopted by the Dispute Settlement Body. Yet, the US failed to comply with the ruling even after the elapse of the 13 months implementation period. It was at this point that Malaysia lodged another complaint that the US was adamant towards lifting the import prohibition of certain shrimp and shrimp products. The Compliance Panel constituted to look into this compliance proceeding ruled that the US measure at contention does not constitute an unjustifiable discrimination between countries where the same conditions prevail and that "the measure is within the scope of the exemptions specified under Article XX of the GATT 1994, as long as the conditions stated in the findings of this Report, in particular the ongoing serious good faith efforts to reach a multilateral agreement, remain satisfied" (Kallummal 2015). Even when this ruling was appealed, the Appellate Body still upheld the findings of the Compliance Panel.

In the case of *EC – Tariff Preferences (2004)*, India brought a complaint against the European Union for extending generalized tariff preferences to a few developing countries (12 of them). The concession was given to the selected countries on three conditions: labour standards, environmental standards, and the war on drugs. The argument of India was that this treatment breached the principles of

unconditionally and non-discrimination. While the Panel ruled that the EU treatment was inconsistent with MFN principle, the Appellate Body rather reversed the Panel's central findings.

Developing countries are mostly discouraged from bringing up complaints to dispute resolution panel of WTO as a result of the negative outcomes this may trigger-off. This was evidenced by the case of *European Communities - Regime for the Importation, Sale and Distribution of Bananas*, where five banana-producing countries: Colombia, Costa Rica, Guatemala, Nicaragua, and Venezuela lodged a complaint against European Community for introducing a regime where banana imports were subjected to tariff rate quota systems on the basis of their country of origin. Before this complaint, the Lomé Convention already provided that bananas imported from former EU territories and developing countries in Africa, the Caribbean and the Pacific (ACP countries) were duty free. The Panel that looked into the matter ruled that the EU banana regime was inconsistent with the MFN requirement. To remedy this, the EU had a negotiation with most of the complainant countries. The settlement was that their export quotas would be increased and the complainants must withdraw the complaints and must not engage in further GATT challenges until December 2002 (Duffy 2021). In this case, Ecuador was given the authority to deploy retaliatory tariffs as a remedy against European Union for violating WTO's principles. However, Ecuador saw no realistic way to retaliate in this regard (Bronckers & Van den Broek 2005). It is very hard and nearly impossible for developing countries such as Ecuador to put up a sufficient retaliatory remedy when their rights under the WTO framework are infringed upon. This adduced evidence in line with the findings of Devarajan, Go, Lakatos, Robinson and Thierfelder (2018) that retaliatory move by developing countries is not a desirable remedy against developing countries that violate WTO's principles.

3.3. Deficiency III: Allowing Reciprocity in Regional Trade Relation

Customs unions and regional trade agreements such as European Union are logical extensions of the automatic reciprocity agreement. Through a means of progressive mutual concessions, such unions work towards eliminating tariff rates and other commercial restrictions among participating nations. According to Duffy (2021), the existence of regional trade agreements prior to the formation of the GATT was sternly defended by powerful countries on the trading platform such as the US, UK and Germany. The proliferation of regional trade agreements (OECD 2004) is also evidence of loopholes in the WTO principles. Ideally, WTO's MFN principle was brought to liberalise trade among members by enhancing multilateral trading system. Allowing the emergence and growth of regional trading system defeats this aim. The exceptions in the MFN rule (Article XXIV, enabling clause and Article V) have

become the rule, thereby undermining the framework of the WTO with respect to “favour-one-favour-all principle”.

Worse still, the trade disputes emanating from the regional trade agreements (RTA) are normally brought to the table of WTO even though some principles of the RTA do not go in line with those of WTO. For instance, in the *Argentina—Footwear Case* where Argentina imposed safeguard measures on all countries with the exception of members of their major regional trade treaty, MERCOSUR; and in the *Brazil— Retreaded Tyres*, where Brazil also imposed import safeguard measures on all countries with the exception of members of their major regional trade treaty (Herbert 2020). When the cases were brought to the WTO’s Appellate Body, the ruling in the *Argentina—Footwear Case* was that Argentina should apply safeguard measures to all countries while in the ruling in the case of *Brazil—Tyres* was that MERCOSUR members are disallowed from modifying their WTO obligations on import restrictions based on their regional trade body.

The concept of reciprocity agreement requires that countries participating in a particular contractual agreement mutually grant to themselves concessions in quotas, tariff rates or other commercial restrictions (Yanai 2001).

WTO has been severely criticised for allowing the establishment of this sort of reciprocity treaty despite the rule-based principle of MFN (Schneider-Petsinger 2020).

4.0. CONCLUSION

The DSU essentially aims at resolving trade issues and eliminating discriminatory trade practices but the exceptions to the rule have spurred a number of trade disputes over the years and also eroded the effectiveness and applicability of the MFN rule upon which the WTO is anchored. A proper functioning of international business operation and trade would require the rule-based regime of the WTO. This regime when tightened enough, defends countries against protectionist tendencies of developed economies, overwhelming regionalism, and aggressive unilateralism that culminate into threats to global integration. However, the rule-based regime of the WTO cannot stand when the dispute resolution mechanism of the organisation is yet to be bereft of power-based inclinations. Reform should start with developing a formal WTO apparatus responsible for monitoring compliance to its ruling. More also, the exceptions to the MFN rule which has turned out to be the rule need to be more carefully applied in setting up of regional trade agreements. Otherwise, the merits of the DSU will be undermined, especially now that the multiplicity of the regional trade treaties increasingly marks a departure from the principles of WTO.

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